

ANALYSIS OF CONCEPTS RELATED TO THE TASKS OF OPERATIONAL-SEARCH ACTIVITIES

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Аннотация. The article analyzes the content, distinctive nature of concepts related to the tasks of operational-search activities and for the first time developed a definition of authorship of these concepts.

Калит сўзлар: crime prevention, crime detection, crime exposure, crime elimination.

Over the past twenty years, the theory and practice of Crime Prevention has developed in western European countries, including the United Kingdom, Belgium, France and Germany, and several practical and systematic measures for Crime Prevention have been implemented. There are two levels of crime prevention in EU member states. These are: social and situational situation.

1. In the social Prevention of crimes, the focus is on changing unfavorable conditions for the formation of an individual's personality, especially microenvironment.

2. In the Prevention of crimes in situational situations, certain categories of criminal actions are obtained by the correct use of forces and means in this situation, depending on the circumstances, at certain times and when a public event is held in certain places, for example, in public places .

There are three levels of crime prevention in the Federal Republic of Germany. These are: 1) social and economic factors are studied as the causes of crimes; 2) by explaining the content of measures of legal influence by police bodies; 3) applying the type of punishment prescribed by law. In the Prevention of organized crimes (such as abuse of career authority, bribery), there are constantly rapid-search measures .

In most European countries, national councils are established that are involved in crime prevention, the main functions of which are: 1) the collection of information, planning, implementation and evaluation of crime prevention programs; 2) Coordination of the activities of the police and other bodies working in this area; 3) public participation; 4) cooperation with the media;

5) implementation of research work; 6) cooperation with legislative bodies determining policies in the field of combating crime; 7) Organization of a seminar-training session on crime prevention.

In the UK state, minimum rules for the organization of security in administrative regions are developed in the Prevention of crimes. In this case, measures such as the implementation of patrol service by the population in cooperation with the police, that is, the organization of duty in criminogenic areas, are widely used, and representatives of this community are given special technical means (handcuffs, radio communication tools, cars) in the effective provision of Service . The main function of the police service is crime prevention, the further functions are to effectively investigate and expose crimes.

Three models of crime prevention activities have been developed in the United States, namely: the public institutions model, the personality safety model, and exposure through the environment. In some states, however, citizens' participation in strengthening law enforcement is financially encouraged by providing information of importance as a result of the implementation of rapid-search prevention, allowing the crime of theft to be avoided by nearly 30 percent.

In the Canadian state, the involvement of citizens in patrol service in the Administrative Region is effectively organized, and the fact that citizens carry out patrols together with police officers directly learns to serve responsibly, increasing the feeling of fearlessness of persons committing crimes in them. Additional posts are also set up in areas with high crime rates at night.

In crime prevention, police criminologists study the causes and conditions that allowed crimes to take place, develop proposals and recommendations for improving police performance, and participate in the development of crime prevention plans, cooperation with government bodies, NGOs and non-profit organizations .

The receipt of crimes in Japan is divided into four systems. These are: 1) the crime prevention system, which covers all areas of Social Life; 2) the system of preventive measures of the state, developed on the basis of a specific goal; 3) the system of institutional control at the state and municipal level; 4) the system of measures for the premature prevention of crimes and the Prevention of repeated crimes .

Criminologist scientists argue that crime prevention is not only a condition affecting concrete criminogenic factors, but also a social phenomenon that requires constant study.

This means that these levels, models and systems of crime prevention are the most effective way to combat crime. In general, the study of crime prevention models, forms and methods used in foreign countries studied (Germany, USA, Canada, Great Britain and Japan) allows in this activity to maintain an adequate provision of members of representatives of all strata of society, feedback on the constant assistance of citizens to the police officer.

In our opinion, the main goal aimed at preventing crimes should be aimed at preventing any harm that is being inflicted or may be inflicted on the individual, society and the state. Based on the feedback from the above specialists and advanced foreign experiences, we give the following definition to the theoretical concepts that make up the main tasks and functions of the tqf when defining our own personal point of view:

prevention of crimes in operational-search activities – a system of general measures aimed at adapting persons prone to committing crimes to social life, preventing the occurrence of a new crime, in cooperation with officials of civil society institutions and other state bodies by competent state bodies;

elimination of crimes in operational – search activities-complex measures to put an end to further criminal activity by stopping the actions of a person preparing, planning, committing a crime by officials of competent state bodies;

stop crimes in operational-search activities – measures aimed at stopping further actions of an individual as a result of external influence until the commission of a crime by officials of competent state bodies (capturing partners, capturing them on the road, on the way to the crime scene);

prevention of crimes in operational-search activities – a system of organizational and tactical, special measures aimed at the premature prevention of crimes committed by officials of competent state bodies or possible future crimes;

detection of crimes in operational-search activities – measures aimed at identifying a socially dangerous act committed on the basis of an application or message received by competent state bodies, officials;

exposing crimes in operational – search activities is the process of fully proving the identification and conduct of a person (persons)who committed a socially dangerous act on the basis of a petition or message received by officials of competent state bodies.

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